

Reactions of Organotin Chlorides. Reactions with Tertiary Amines

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Complexes of the type $\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2\cdot\text{L}$ (where $\text{L}=\text{triphenylamine}$), $\text{R}_2\text{SnCl}_2\cdot 2\text{L}$ (where $\text{R}=\text{-CH}_3$ and $\text{L}=\text{Et}_3\text{N}$), $\text{R}_2\text{SnCl}_2\cdot\text{L}$ [(where $\text{R}=\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$, $\text{-nC}_4\text{H}_9$ and $\text{L}=\text{Et}_3\text{N}$) and (when $\text{R}=\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$, $\text{L}=\text{Ph}_3\text{N}$)], $\text{ROSnCl}_2\cdot 2\text{L}$ [(where $\text{R}=\text{-CH}_3$, $\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5$ and $\text{-tC}_4\text{H}_9$ and $\text{L}=\text{Et}_3\text{N}$ and $(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_2\text{N}$) and $\text{ROSnCl}_2\cdot\text{L}$ [(where $\text{R}=\text{-tC}_4\text{H}_9$ and $\text{L}=(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_2\text{N}$)] have been prepared. Infrared spectra of complexes were examined to elucidate plausible structures.

A survey of literature revealed that the reactions of tertiary amines and amino oxides with organotin (IV) chlorides and monoalkoxytin trichlorides had not been studied in detail¹⁻⁹. Complexes like tin bis-acetatodibutyl (triethylamine) and tin dichlorodiethyl (triethylamine) have been reported¹⁰. The reaction may be represented as follows:

A patent describes the triethanol-amine adducts of the type, $\text{R}_2\text{Sn X} \cdot \text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_3$ (where $\text{R}=\text{Ph}$, alkyl, $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$, AcO)¹¹. In view of this it was considered worthwhile to synthesise complexes of triorgano, diorganotin(IV) chlorides and monoalkoxytin trichlorides with a variety of tertiary amines like triethylamine, triethanolamine and triphenylamine.

Experimental

Ethoxy group in the complexes was estimated as reported by Mehrotra¹². Solvents were purified and dried by standard methods¹³. Organotin(IV) chlorides (Alpha Inorganics Inc. and Eastman Organic Chemicals Co.) and amines (B.D.H. and Riedel) were used. Monoalkoxytin

trichlorides were prepared by the method of Bradley et al¹⁴.

Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded as nujol mull in the range of 4000-250 cm^{-1} . Elemental analyses of the complexes are given in Table 1.

The complexes were prepared by the direct interaction of the Lewis acids and bases by one of the following methods:

Method (1):

A solution of organotin(IV) chloride or monoalkoxytin trichloride (4 m. mole) in 30 ml of a suitable solvent was added to a solution of an excess quantity of base in 50 ml of the same solvent. Reaction mixture was refluxed and stirred for several hours. The excess solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the desired product was precipitated by the addition of petroleum ether (60-80°). The complexes were dried in vacuum.

Method (2):

More concentrated solutions of the organotin Lewis acids and the ligands were taken. The

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Complex	Colour	M. P. °C	Found %				Calculated %			
				C	H	N	OEt	C	H	N	OEt
A.	$\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_3\text{N}$	Pink	112°	39.7	8.25	6.90	—	39.9	8.5	6.64	—
B.	$\text{Bu}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot \text{Et}_3\text{N}$	White	81°	41.2	7.90	3.25	—	41.4	8.14	3.45	—
C.	$\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot \text{Et}_3\text{N}$	White	130°	48.3	5.0	3.20	—	48.5	5.01	3.10	—
D.	$\text{MeO}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_3\text{N}$	Yellow	92°	34.08	7.0	5.95	—	34.06	7.3	6.1	—
E.	$\text{EtO}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_3\text{N}$	White	140°	35.3	7.23	6.01	9.8	35.55	7.41	5.98	9.53
F.	$\text{Bu}^t\text{OSnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_3\text{N}$	White	d.	38.3	7.8	5.7	—	38.6	7.64	5.5	—
G.	$\text{MeOSnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{TEA}$	White	137°	28.9	6.0	5.0	—	28.18	5.97	5.05	—
H.	$\text{EtOSnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{TEA}$	White	215°	29.43	6.1	5.1	8.0	29.5	6.16	4.92	7.9
I.	$\text{Bu}^t\text{OSnCl}_2 \cdot \text{TEA}$	White	118°	26.66	5.8	3.1	—	26.85	5.74	3.18	—
J.	$\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot \text{Ph}_3\text{N}$	White	82°	61.5	4.5	2.41	—	61.12	4.25	2.95	—
K.	$\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot \text{Ph}_3\text{N}$	Green	144°	65.45	4.65	3.0	—	65.53	4.76	2.98	—

TEA = Triethanolamine.

precipitated compound was filtered and washed with suitable solvents and dried in vacuum.

Results and Discussion

All complexes are white solids except A and D which are pink and light yellow respectively in colour. Complex A is soluble in common organic solvents while J and K are insoluble. Complexes B to I are insoluble in common organic solvents and have sharp melting points. The conductivity measurement does not support their ionic nature. The measurements of their molecular weights in boiling benzene give much lower values suggesting dissociation.

Infrared

A comparison of the spectra of complexes G, H and I with that of free triethanolamine indicates the overlapping of $\nu(\text{OH}-\text{N})$ or $\nu(\text{OH}+\text{NH})$ in the spectral region from $3350-3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to $3360-2980\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The absorption for $(\text{C}-\text{N})$ bond in all the complexes are difficult to note in the spectral region $1300-900\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Since nitrogen is a better donor, it is likely that the coordination in the complexes G, H and I takes place through nitrogen. The identification of two new absorptions at 430 ± 7 and $370 \pm 6\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are probably due to $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{N})$ stretching vibrations which is an evidence of coordination from nitrogen atom^{7,15,16}.

The $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$ vibration in the spectra of complex A is identified at $568-562\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In complex B two absorptions at 600 cm^{-1} and 521 cm^{-1} are assigned for asymmetric and symmetric $(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$ vibrations respectively^{17,18}. The absorptions for complexes C and J at 283 ± 1 are assigned for $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$ vibrations²¹. The $\nu_{\text{av}}(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$ vibrations in the spectra of complexes C and J are expected to fall round 240 cm^{-1} which could not be recorded^{19,20}. An absorption at 278 cm^{-1} is assigned for $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$ vibration in the spectra of complex K.

Absorptions due to $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{O})$ bond in complexes D, E, F, G, H and I are assigned at 566 cm^{-1} , 554 cm^{-1} , 539 cm^{-1} , 575 cm^{-1} , 556 cm^{-1} and 522 cm^{-1} respectively^{2,22-24}.

The $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{Cl})$ vibration in the spectra of complexes D, E, F, G, H and I are observed at $327 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$,^{1,2,25,26}. The shifting of $(\text{Sn}-\text{Cl})$ vibration in the lower spectral region indicates the presence of coordinated base in these complexes. The $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{Cl})$ vibration in the spectra of organotin chlorides is reported round $350 \pm 10\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ¹⁷⁻²⁰ which is shifted in the spectra of complexes A, B, C, J and K below 260 cm^{-1} ²⁶. The shifting of $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{Cl})$ vibration in the lower spectral region is also an evidence of coordinated base in these complexes.

Structure :

The absence of $\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$ vibration in the infrared spectra of complex A in the region $550-500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggests a coordination number of six for tin atom with a trans alignment of the methyl groups in an octahedral structure²⁰. Complexes B, C, J and K have penta coordinated tin atom. In the infrared spectra of complex B both $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$ and $\nu_{\text{av}}(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$ vibrations are observed while $\nu_{\text{sy}}(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$ vibration in the spectra of complexes C and J is expected to lie beyond the recorded range of the spectra. Hence butyl and phenyl groups in the complex B, C and J are probably non-linear in the trigonal bipyramidal geometry. There is only one band at 278 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectra of complex K for $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{Sn}-\text{C})$ vibration. Hence Ph_3Sn group is planar in the trigonal bipyramidal geometry^{19,20,27}.

Complexes D, E, F, G and H are hexa coordinate compounds and probably have octahedral structures. Complex I appears to be penta coordinate according to its empirical formula. But it can also have a dimeric structure²⁸ in which each tin atom is six coordinate in an octahedral environment. Further, absorption at 522 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectra of complex I is probably due to a ring vibration of the $\text{Sn}-\text{O}$ four membered ring²⁸.

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